

Title: On the particle motion in paleo-magnetosphere during the geomagnetic polarity reversal

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Description of contents: This archive contains input data files and 3D data files from simulations of the Space Weather Modeling Framework (SWMF), as well as 3D motion trajectory data of test-particle model tracking.

- The swmf-input folder contains the upstream solar wind input condition of SWMF.
- The mgt-3d-simu folder contains 3d magnetospheric simulation data at 765 ka and 774.5 ka.
- The 756ka_3dtrace-data folder contains test-particle tracing simulation data at 765 ka.
- The 774-5ka_3dtrace-data folder contains test-particle tracing simulation data at 774.5 ka.